

Magnetism of Cobaltic Complexes

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Magnetic susceptibilities of a number of cobaltic complexes, measured by Gouy's method, indicate a substantial contribution of the second-order paramagnetism of cobalt atom. The observed values for the residual paramagnetism are compared with those calculated on the basis of the ligand-field theory of Griffith and Orgel.

Early investigation of magnetic susceptibilities of cobaltic complexes by Rosenbohm¹ showed that the observed molecular susceptibilities were very much different from those calculated from the diamagnetism of the constituent atoms on the basis of additivity rule; so he proposed a constitutive correction of $+55 \times 10^{-6}$ for the hexammine, $+60 \times 10^{-6}$ for the pentammine, $+73 \times 10^{-6}$ for the tetrammine, and $+97 \times 10^{-6}$ for the triammine series. Kernahan and Sienko² from the study of magnetic susceptibilities of two isoelectronic cobaltic pentammines showed, however, that the constitutive correction for pentammine was much higher ($\sim 150 \times 10^{-6}$). They further observed that the value of the constitutive correction was not a constant for a particular series of amines, but there was always an effect of co-ordinated groups on the electronic distribution in the entire complex. Constitutive correction constants for various amines have also been reported by Belova and Syrkin³. This earlier work indicates that the observed susceptibilities of cobaltic complexes have a significant contribution due to second-order paramagnetism, independent of temperature, although the spins of cobaltic ion are paired in complex formation.

The interest in the magnetic properties of cobaltic complexes has revived recently owing to the development in the ligand-field theory. Griffith and Orgel⁴ were able to calculate on the basis of this theory the amount of the second-order paramagnetism (x_p) for the octahedral complexes of trivalent cobalt. They have shown that in these complexes only one excited state (${}^1T_{1g}$) contributes to the residual paramagnetism; knowing the energy separation between this state and the ground state (${}^1A_{1g}$), the amount of x_p can be calculated from the relation:

$$x_p = \frac{8}{3} N \left(\frac{e\hbar}{2mc} \right)^2 \frac{24}{E} = \frac{4.085}{K} \quad \dots (1)$$

where E and K represent the energy separation in energy units and wave numbers, respectively, between the ground and the excited states ${}^1A_{1g}$ and ${}^1T_{1g}$. Using the values of K , obtained from the absorption maximum for the low-intensity band in the spectra of these complexes, they estimated a value of $+105 \times 10^{-6}$ for x_p in the hexammines. The values

1. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1919, 93, 693.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 77, 1978.
3. *Neorg. Khim. Akad. Nauk, S.S.S.R.*, 1965, 30, 109.
4. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 53, 601.

of the constitutive correction constants, reported by earlier workers, have the same order of magnitude as those calculated from this theory, but the agreement is rather unsatisfactory. The data so far available on the magnetic susceptibilities of these complexes are quite meagre and are not helpful in testing the theory rigorously.

The theoretical work of Griffith and Orgel⁴ has, however, found support in the NMR of Co³⁺ in these complexes. The experimental data on chemical shifts of Co³⁺, observed by Proctor and Yu⁵, Freeman *et al.*⁶, and Dharmatti *et al.*⁷, on a number of octahedral complexes, indicate that the shifts are predominantly due to the second-order paramagnetic term arising from the mixing of ¹A_{1g} and ¹T_{1g}. Griffith and Orgel⁴ applied their theory to the calculation of the chemical-shift parameter for a few complexes for which data of Proctor and Yu⁵ were available and found a satisfactory agreement between the theory and experiment. Dharmatti and Kanekar⁸ made similar calculations and found that the theory satisfactorily explained NMR chemical shifts of Co³⁺ for many octahedral complexes. From the chemical shift data they could also establish an order for the strength of various ligands; the contribution of the second-order paramagnetism to the chemical-shift parameter was found to decrease in the order:

i.e., in the same order as increasing ligand-field strengths in these complexes.

As the Griffith and Orgel theory satisfactorily explains the NMR data of these complexes, a careful study of the magnetic susceptibilities of cobaltic complexes has been undertaken to examine the theory from the magnetic susceptibility data.

EXPERIMENTAL

Several cobaltic complexes were prepared by standard methods and their purity was checked by estimation of cobalt as cobalt sulphate. Magnetic susceptibility of cobaltic complexes was determined in the solid state by the Gouy method in the usual manner. Nickel chloride solution (30%) was used as a standard for calibration of the tube.

The results obtained are recorded in Table I in which χ_g represents the susceptibility per g. and χ_M , the molar susceptibility. In all cases measurements were made on three or four samples prepared independently. χ_g values are a mean of measurements on several fillings. All values of χ are expressed in units of 10^{-6} C.G.S.

DISCUSSION

Van Vleck's expression⁹ for the molar susceptibility of a polyatomic molecule in the E state can be expressed in the form:

$$\chi_M = \chi_D + \chi_P \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

5. *Phys. Rev.*, 1951, **81**, 20.

6. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1957, **242A**, 455.

7. Symposium on the Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds, Nat. Acad. of Sciences, India, 1959.

8. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1959, **31**, 1436.

9. "The Theory of Electric and Magnetic Susceptibilities", Oxford University Press, London 1932.

where x_D is the diamagnetic susceptibility of all the constituent atoms in the molecule and x_P is the residual paramagnetism, independent of temperature.

TABLE I

No.	Complex.	% Cobalt.		$x_D \times 10^6$.	$x_P \times 10^6$.	$K(\text{cm}^{-1})$.	x_P Co.		Orbital reduction factor, k .
		Found.	Calc.				Obs.	Calc.	
1.	$K_3[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6]$	17.7	17.7	-0.310 ± 0.003	-103.0	32150 ⁶	55.5	127	0.7
2.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$	22.3	22.3	-0.230 ± 0.003	-63.8	21000 ¹⁰	110	104	0.8
3.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CO}_3]\text{NO}_3$	22.1	22.2	-0.107 ± 0.003	-28.5	19670 ¹¹	115	207	0.8
4.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$	23.5	23.5	-0.115 ± 0.004	-28.2	18720 ¹²	132	218	0.8
5.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NO}_2]\text{Cl}_2$	23.1	22.8	-0.147 ± 0.0002	-38.3	21840 ¹³	115	187	0.8
6.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{CO}_3]\text{NO}_3$	23.5	23.3	+0.070 ± 0.0008	+18.7	19000 ¹¹	147	214	0.8
7.	<i>cis</i> - $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{NO}_3$	21.0	21.0	+0.322 ± 0.003	+71.8	22510 ¹³	105	181	1.0
8.	<i>trans</i> - $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{NO}_3$	21.0	21.0	+0.075 ± 0.0004	+21.2	22630 ¹¹	145	181	0.9
9.	$\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$	11.4	11.3	+0.163 ± 0.0009	+69.7	20670 ¹⁴	178	197	1.0
10.	$\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NO}_2)_2$	23.8	23.8	+0.381 ± 0.004	+04.5	23210 ¹³	165	178	1.0
11.	$[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]\text{Cl}_3$	14.4	14.8	-0.377 ± 0.0007	-151	21400 ¹⁰	104	180	0.7
12.	<i>trans</i> - $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{NO}_3$	17.6	17.7	-0.144 ± 0.003	-47.9	23300 ¹¹	101	175	0.8
13.	<i>cis</i> - $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{NO}_3$	17.0	17.7	+0.083 ± 0.0009	-27.6	23000 ¹¹	176	177	1.0
14.	$[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	6.7	6.7	-0.330 ± 0.001	-297	22230 ¹⁵	163	184	0.9

Assuming Pascal's additivity law, the x_D term in all complexes was calculated from the reported values of the susceptibilities of the constituent atoms. Pascal's values for C, H, N, and C $\equiv$ N and the relevant constitutive correction constants for various types of the linkages in organic ligands were used. The values used for diamagnetic susceptibilities of other groups are: $\text{NH}_3 = -17.1^{16}$; $\text{NO}_2 = -13.1^{17}$; $\text{Co}^{3+} = 10^{18}$; $\text{Cl}^- = -22.1^{19}$; $\text{NO}_3^- = -18.9^{20}$; $\text{CO}_3^{2-} = -29.5^{20}$; $\text{K}^+ = -13.5^{21}$; $\text{Na}^+ = -5.2^{22}$.

10. Jorgenson, 10th Solvay Conference, Brussels, 1956.

11. Yamada and Tsuchida, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1953, 26, 15.

12. Linhard and Weigel, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1951, 266, 40.

13. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1951, 267, 113.

14. Tsuchida, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1938, 13, 388.

15. Yamasaki, *ibid.*, p. 130.

16. Gray and Farquharson, *Phil. Mag.*, 1930, 10, 191.

17. Trew, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, 32, 1660.

18. Klamm, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1941, 246, 347.

19. Kido, *Sci. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1932, 21, 149.

20. Trew, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1941, 37, 476.

21. Bradley, *Phil. Mag.*, 1931, 11, 787.

22. Eshling, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1927 114A, 181,

The choice of these values is arbitrary as widely divergent data have been reported in literature and it is difficult to choose any one value as more reliable than the other. The values of x_p were then obtained by subtracting x_D values from the observed x_M of the complexes. The values x_p (obs.) are shown in column 7 of the table.

On the basis of Griffith and Orgel's theory, one expects a linear relation between x_p (obs.) and $1/K = \lambda$, the wave length for maximum absorption for the band arising from 3d electrons. The values of K have been reported by various authors such as Jorgensen¹⁰, Tsuchida¹⁴ etc. (col. 6, Table I). Some of these values have been confirmed by the present authors from the absorption spectra of the samples prepared for this work. The plot obtained for x_p (obs.) and λ is shown in Fig. 1. It is approximately linear although a few points deviate considerably.

FIG. 1.

x_p values have also been calculated from relation (1) using Δ value in column 6. Although the calculated values of x_p (8th column) are of the same order of magnitude as the observed x_p values, the agreement is not better than 40%. Griffith and Orgel⁴ estimated the probable errors in their theoretical calculations to be not more than 20%. A lack of good agreement between the observed and calculated x_p values may partly be due to the uncertainties in the values of the diamagnetic susceptibilities used for evaluation of the x_D term. It is well known that the observed molar susceptibilities, obtained for the same substance by various investigators, often differ considerably. Further, the susceptibilities of atoms and ions, deduced from the molar susceptibility data, often differ from one another. For example, the reported values of the susceptibility of Na^+ range from— 4.0 to — 10 and therefore depending on the choice of x_{DA} used, a range of values of x_p can be obtained. For three compounds, namely, $\text{Na}_2[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6] \text{Cl}_3$, and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4 \text{CO}_3] \text{NO}_3$, chosen at random, values of x_p have been calculated by using the extreme values of diamagnetic susceptibilities of the constituent ions reported in literature. These are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Complex.	x of diamagnetic ions.	x_p	
		Obs.	Calc.
$\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$	$x_{\text{NO}_2^+}$ 10.4; 4.0	180.5	
		170.3	107
$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$	x_{Cl^-} 28.0; 10.5	132.8	
		107.3	104
$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{CO}_3]\text{NO}_3$	$x_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}$ 30.2; $x_{\text{NO}_3^-}$ 10.5 $x_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}$ 22.2; $x_{\text{NO}_3^-}$ 14.2	146.6	
		133.5	214

It is seen that the x_p values thus, obtained, are still less than those calculated from the theory, indicating that although the discrepancy is partly due to the uncertainties in x_D values, in general, the observed x_p values are always less than the theoretical estimates. These results probably reflect bonding effects on the susceptibilities of these complexes. The theory of Griffith and Orgel assumes that the t_{2g} orbitals approximate very closely to d orbitals. This would, however, not be the case in presence of bonding. One way to allow for any departure from pure d orbitals is to introduce an orbital-reduction factor, k , which affects the matrix elements of L , but not of S and therefore will have a net effect on the magnetic susceptibility when the matrix elements of the spin moment are small compared to that of the orbital moment. For the case of octahedral cobaltic complexes, the expression (1) can therefore be modified as shown by Griffith²³ by introducing a factor k^2 on the right hand side. For pure d orbitals $k=1$, and for low-spin complexes of the first transition series, k will be close to unity, $(1-k)$ being the measure of the deviation of actual orbitals from being pure d orbitals. Values of k have been calculated for all the compounds studied in this investigation from the ratio of x_p (obs.) to x_p (calc.) and are shown in the last column of Table I. These values are found to vary between 0.7 and 1.0. Results show a trend similar to that observed by Asmussen and Ballhausen²⁴.

Previous works of Rosenbohm¹ and Belova and Syrkin³ show that the constitutive correction constants increase in the order: hexammine < pentammine < tetrammine < triammine. Our results indicate approximately similar trend in x_p values. It is very unlikely, however, that all pentammines have the same constitutive correction constant as found by Rosenbohm¹. The results obtained in this investigation show that in the pentammines, x_p varies, depending on the type of the ligands or groups present in the co-ordination complex. This is in conformity with the ligand-field theory. It is clear from Griffith-Orgel's theory that the energy separation between the ground and the excited state depends on the strength of the ligand and will affect the x_p values. The greater the separation between the two states, the smaller is the contribution of the x_p value to the molar susceptibility of the complex. From Table I the x_p contribution appears to decrease in the order:

This is consistent with the order of increasing ligand fields reported for various ligands by Griffith and Orgel⁴.

23. "Theory of Transition Metal Ions", Cambridge University Press, 1961, p. 284.

24. *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1957, 11, 470.

Freeman *et al.*⁶ have shown that the chemical-shift parameter, σ , in the NMR of Co^{59} in cobaltic complexes can be written in the form

$$\sigma = A - (B_0/\Delta_j)$$

where the first term represents the contribution due to the diamagnetic term and the second term comes from the second-order paramagnetism arising from the matrix elements of the orbital angular momentum operator between the states ${}^1A_{1g}$ and ${}^1T_{1g}$. The cobalt nuclear resonance frequency of the j th member of the series of octahedral complex compounds is therefore, expressed by the relation:

$$\nu_j = \frac{1}{2\pi} \gamma H_0 (1 - \sigma) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \gamma H_0 \left(1 + A + \frac{B_0}{\Delta_j}\right) \quad \dots (5)$$

where ν_j is the resonance frequency of the j th member; B_0 is a constant, the value of which in this particular case has been evaluated to be 33.4 ($1/r_3$)_{3d} cm^{-1} (cf. Freeman *et al.*⁶) and $1/\Delta_j$ is the wave length (λ) corresponding to the absorption maximum in the electronic spectrum arising from $d-d$ transitions.

The validity of this relation was tested by Freeman *et al.*⁶ by plotting a graph of ν against λ for various octahedral complexes and they found the plot to be approximately a straight line for symmetrical complexes from which B_0 could be evaluated to be $+450 \pm 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

It is possible to evaluate the constant B_0 from the slope of the straight line drawn by plotting the observed x_p values against λ (Fig. 1) on the following considerations. Expression (1) can be written as

$$x_p = \frac{1}{2} N \left(\frac{e}{2mc} \right)^2 \frac{1}{\bar{E}} (O/L^2/O) \quad \dots (6)$$

where $\bar{E}$ is the energy separation in ergs between the ground and excited states and $(O/L^2/O)$ is the matrix element of the angular momentum operator.

Expressing $\bar{E}$ in terms of λ , the wave length of the absorption maximum of the low-intensity band, we get

$$x_p = \frac{1}{2} N \left(\frac{e}{2mc} \right)^2 \times \frac{1}{hc} \times \lambda (O/L^2/O) \quad \dots (7)$$

Hence the slope (S) of the straight line, obtained by plotting x_p against λ , will be given by

$$S = \frac{1}{2} N \left(\frac{e}{2mc} \right)^2 \frac{1}{hc} (O/L^2/O) \quad \dots (8)$$

Now, one makes use of Griffith and Orgel's approximation for σ as

$$\sigma = A - \frac{e^2}{3 m^2 c^2 \bar{E}} \left(\frac{1}{r^3} \right) (O/L^2/O) \quad \dots (9)$$

This reduces to

$$\sigma = A - \frac{B_0}{\Delta j}, \text{ where}$$

$$B_0 = \frac{e^2}{3 m^2 c^2 h c} \times \frac{1}{a_0^3} \left(\frac{1}{r^3} \right)_{3d} (O / L^2 / O) \quad \dots (10)$$

Combining (10) with (8), we get

$$S = \frac{N}{2} \frac{a_0^3}{(1/r^3)_{3d}} B_0$$

Assuming the value of $(1/r^3)$ for cobaltic ion to be the same as that used by Freeman *et al.*⁶, the value of B_0 can be calculated from the slope of the straight line. Table III records the value obtained for B_0 along with those obtained from NMR data of Freeman *et al.*⁶ and Dharmatti *et al.*⁷ The agreement between the B_0 values obtained from magnetic susceptibility and NMR data is quite good. All the values agree reasonably well with that calculated theoretically (last column).

TABLE III

Extreme diamagnetic values of the ions.

	Susceptibility.	NMR.	Theory.
		450 ⁶	
B_0 (cm ⁻¹)	647	421 ⁸	704